

Transition towards environment friendly consumer products by co-creation of an oxidoreductase foundry

GA No 101000607

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D1.3: Work-on data from interviews, round table talks and world cafés

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List of abbreviations and definitions

AREA	Anticipate, reflect, engage, and act
CDP	Communication and dissemination Plan
CLIB	Cluster for Industrial Biotechnology (Germany)
D	Deliverable
DMP	Data Management Plan
DTA	Data Transfer Agreement
EC	European Commission
EEA	European Economic Area
EEN	Enterprise Europe Network EEN
EU	European Union
FNR	Food and Natural Resources
GA	Grant agreement
GDPR	General data protection regulation
GMO	Genetically modified organisms
ISO	International Standardisation Organisation
KSA	Key Stakeholder Area
M	Milestone
MC	Management Committee for OXIPRO (one representative per partner)
NGO's	Non-Governmental Organisations
R&I	Research and Innovation
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
AB	Advisory Board
SC	Scientific Committee for OXIPRO (WP leaders)
T	Task
WP	Work Package

Preamble

This deliverable covers the work conducted between M1 and M18. An updated (final) version will be submitted as D1.9 in M24. This is a brief overview of work conducted in context within D1.3:

- Developing a strategy to align with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) including the development of data transfer agreements for incoming and outgoing data.
- Contribution to WP9 (Ethics): Identify, test, and deploy data protection compliant tools
- Identify and implement data protection compliant storage media
- Monthly security checks of the tools used for stakeholder engagement.
- Inform, train, and include partners in the process of stakeholder engagement by mail, webinars, and training (co-creation)
- Preparation and execution of a webinar for OXIPRO's consortium on stakeholder engagement.
- Preparation and execution of a seminar for OXIPRO's consortium on "How to collect and share personal data".
- Preparation and distribution of data collection sheets (mailing with one repetition).
- Preparation and executing of 10 cappuccino talks with OXIPRO's partners to explain the procedure of data collection and the use of the datasheet.
- Developing questions for survey test run.
- Survey test run e-mails with links included to survey.
- Preparation, design, and testing e-mails with respective links and QR codes directing to the survey that is hosted on another platform.
- Research on potentially relevant stakeholders in addition to partners' contacts.
- Preparation, testing and sending e-mails to stakeholders.
- Data collection from e-mails and survey participation and analysis.
- Preparation and execution of a co-creation webinar with introduction to persona modeling and practical exercise.
- Preparation and executing a co-creation session at the annual consortium meeting.
- Preparation and presenting WP1 at OXIPRO's kick-off meeting, Management Committee (MC) and Scientific committee (SC) meetings.
- Preparation and submission of documentation of risk assessment of delay.
- Preparation and submission of measures for the risk mitigation plan.
- Preparation of a stakeholder event on circular economy and life cycle assessment planned as an additional event to the annual consortium meeting in June 2022.

- 14 bulks of e-mail to stakeholders.
- Categorisation of information from incoming data for tailored mailing
- Meeting to discuss how to proceed the coordinator and SC members.
- Research to collect stakeholders for the list.
- Summarising how stakeholder engagement plans are to be developed to raise awareness information of partners resulting in the publication “10 simple rules on HOW to develop a stakeholder engagement Plan” [4]
- Distribution and advertisement of the publication within the consortium.
- Participating in MC/SC and WP meetings and addressing the problem/asking for support.

Summary

The vision of OXIPRO is to contribute to the transition towards greener sunscreens, home textiles, nutraceuticals, and detergents, and to the EU Bioeconomy Strategy. This will be done by building an open and collaborative cross-border, cross-sectoral innovation ecosystem that fosters the development of novel enzymes - and specifically oxidoreductases - for environment-friendly consumer products. To achieve this goal, interaction with and engagement of stakeholders becomes crucial.

OXIPRO sees its stakeholders as those individuals, groups, or organisations who may affect, be affected by, or perceive themselves to be affected by its activities or outcomes. Four thematic areas were identified from which these stakeholders originate: **Research, Industry, Society and Policy (STAKEHOLDER AREAS)**. To maximise OXIPRO's impact requires a clear understanding of the interests and influence of the stakeholders and a strategy to address their needs. D1.3 is based on the findings generated by the first information exchange with multiple stakeholders.

The aim of this deliverable is to analyse the interaction and feedback received by stakeholder interactions and to create an interdisciplinary collaborative ecosystem aligned to the process dimensions of anticipate, reflect, engage, and act (AREA). This will be achieved by bringing together stakeholders, promoting data exchange, knowledge sharing, business opportunities and capacity building. Outcomes will be considered for internal use (responsiveness) and will also be used to generate a catalogue of recommendations to address aspects in future exploitation measures. Information will also feed into a social impact assessment (WP6).

D1.3 is an independent document that analyses, evaluates and uses OXIPRO's approach and interaction with stakeholders to reflect and optimize internal processes and to actively involve the public in project design. This is underpinned by an ethos of Open Science and RRI.

Definitions

STAKEHOLDER	Individuals, groups or organisations who are directly or indirectly affected by OXIPRO's activities or who have an interest in OXIPROs activities and /or outcomes or who are relevant for the projects progress and success
STAKEHOLDER REGISTER	List of stakeholders
KEY STAKEHOLDER AREA	Research, politics, economy, and society as a superordinate area to which the stakeholders will be allocated
STAKEHOLDER GROUPS	Individuals, groups, or organisations from stakeholder sectors who have a legitimate interest in the course or outcome of OXIPRO

1 Introduction - Purpose

Deliverable 1.3: Work-on data from interviews, round table talks and world cafés.

Description from GA: The multi-actor stakeholder group (gathering research, industry, and policy stakeholders) will be engaged by active inclusion in the form of at least two round table talks and at least two world cafés during the 1st and the 3rd year. Stakeholders will help understanding the challenges of the practical and technical implementation at institutional, administrative, and monetary level and which needs to be overcome to enable OXIPRO's innovation transfer. One round table talk will be organized with the multi-actor stakeholders and providing links with project officer and policy officers. Another round table talk will be organized as a joint policy meeting with sister FNR-16 projects and policy makers to agree on a harmonized form to deliver results for efficient feedback into policymaking. Findings of the round table talks will be used to develop questions to be addressed in the world cafés and enter research agenda roadmaps, feasibility studies and market replication analyses (T.1.3). Within the world cafés multiple stakeholders will get together to discuss identified inefficiencies and to develop co-creative solutions towards the delivery of targeted innovation-led solutions. One world café will take place with representatives of business/industry and consumer associations. Another world café will be open for a broader spectrum of participants, targeting the potential end-users. Outcomes of the world cafés will identify core questions to be processed in co-creation workshops with members of the consortium.

2 Objectives and scope

D1.3 is a living document, consisting of the work-on data from interviews, round table talks and world cafés. Its content will reflect if and how stakeholders' opinions, attitudes, regulations, requirements, policies change over time. An updated (final) version of D1.3 will be provided in D1.9 in M24.

The objectives and scope of D1.3 are:

1. To foster anticipatory and reflexive governance of the project
2. To develop questions to be addressed in the world cafés
3. To anticipate, reflect feedback of the different stakeholder groups
4. To deliver results for efficient feedback into policymaking
5. To deliver results for efficient feedback in OXIPRO's research agenda roadmaps (engage and act)
6. To support communication and dissemination of OXIPRO results and benefits

In D1.3 we will identify different stakeholders, categorise them into different priority groups and start building a community which should ensure greater acceptance and wider applicability of the project results. The objectives of D1.3 will be addressed by the following activities:

- Application of the measures developed in D1.1 (the stakeholder mapping methodology)
- Analysis of the initial results of the surveys, which will be extended during the project period
- Defining questions and core value propositions for all product lines and their stakeholder categories to be used for further communication and engagement activities
- Preparation of a first draft of a strategy paper as a result of the Cluster ‘Enzymes for Greener Products’ collaboration¹
- Preparation and running of round table talks and world cafés
- Preparation of a policy meeting

2.1 Relation to other WP, deliverables, and tasks

D1.3 influences and forms the basis of workflows in several WPs listed in Table 1.

Table 1 List of WPs, Tasks and Deliverables which are dependent on or influenced by D1.3

WP	Task	Deliverable
1	T.1.1. Stakeholder Engagement T.1.1. Policy brief T.1.2. Capacity building	D1.4
2	T.2.4. In silico bioprospecting modules	
4	T.4.1. Host selection, cloning and small-scale production T.4.3. Process simulation/modelling and large-scale enzyme production	
5	T.5.5. Novel Opportunities	
6	T.6.2. Social and economic sustainability T.6.3. Circularity of value-chains	D6.2
7	T.7.1. Communication and Dissemination plan, social media, and project website T.7.3. Networking, events, and publications T.7.4. Social awareness on consumer products of the future	D7.1, D7.2, D7.3, D7.4

¹ This Cluster gathered the 4 projects funded under the call FNR-16-2020 “Enzymes for more environment-friendly consumer products (call Food and Natural Resources)”: EnXylaScope (Grant Agreement no 101000831), FuturEnzyme (Grant Agreement no 101000327), OXIPRO (Grant Agreement no 101000607) and RADICALZ (Grant Agreement no 101000560).

3 Methodology

3.1 Stakeholder engagement

OXIPRO's multi stakeholder engagement strategy entails several AREA activities that will influence the trajectory of OXIPRO's research and innovation actions (Table 2).

Table 2 OXIPRO's AREA strategy to engage with stakeholders

AREA	User-centred dimension	Multi-actor dimension	Intraconsortium dimension
Anticipate	Consumer interviews (WP1), Habit surveys (WP7), Survey of ethical, legal, and societal concerns (WP1), Risk analysis (WP6)	Landscape analysis (WP1), Overall sustainability (WP6), Risk assessment (WP6), Market analysis and feasibility studies (WP1)	Lecture series (WP1), Scale-up modelling (WP4); Co-creation workshops (WP1)
Reflect	Awareness-raising campaigns (WP7), Meet-a-Scientist (WP1), Design-thinking, Persona Modelling, Consumer journey mapping (WP1).	Life cycle thinking; Circular Economy (WP6); Policy briefs and reports (WP1)	Open Science & FAIR data; Life cycle thinking
Engage	Surveys, open co-creative events (WP1, WP7), consumer panellists' (WP5)	Policy meetings, Policy workshops, Open policy events (WP1), round table talks, world cafes (WP1),	Innovation Boot Camp, Co-creative workshops (WP1), Consortium meetings (WP8)
Act	Contingency plan, Consortium meetings, Management committee, Scientific committee, Manager roles, Advisory Board (WP8), Technology adjustments (WP2-WP5), Consortium agreement (WP8), Data management plan (WP8), SOPs (WP1), ISO standards (WP1, WP6), Open science policy (WP8)		

4 Practical implementation

4.1 Interviews, surveys and questionnaires (month 6-48)

Semi-structured interviews with consumers and consumer organizations to elicit views on key challenges (e.g., GMO issues) relating to OXIPRO will be executed. In addition, a survey based on literature and databases will identify national regulations that promote or hamper the application of the new enzymes and show potential opportunities or risks for introducing the technologies developed in OXIPRO. At least 20 interviews with representatives from the participating partner countries' policymakers will draw out views. The major outcome of this task will be two policy briefs relating to the European Bioeconomy strategy and other relevant strategies, outlining rationales for policy alternatives or courses of action we recommend because of the findings.

4.1.1 Tools

For the implementation of the surveys, it is necessary to work with tools that meet the requirements of data protection. When selecting these, we looked exclusively for those that process the data on

European and, ideally, German servers. After a careful search we decided to use the rapidmail platform to send the information as an email with the link to the survey platform QUESTIONSTAR.

Rapidmail (<https://www.rapidmail.com/>)

Rapidmail is a fully GDPR compliant newsletter software that can be used to reliably send bulk emails. As a newsletter tool from Germany, data protection is top priority for the provider who collaborates with an external data protection entity - Keyed - to ensure that rapidmail always remains 100% GDPR-compliant. The servers are located exclusively in Germany. The data protection and cookie policy are accessible here: <https://www.rapidmail.de/datenschutz-kundenbereich>

QUESTIONSTAR (www.questionstar.de)

QUESTIONSTAR is one of the most advanced tools for online surveys and is GDPR compliant. It has all the features and functions needed to easily create, conduct, and analyse professional online surveys. To increase data security within QUESTIONSTAR, it is possible to store personal data separately. The responses of the subjects are then not contained in one file when the data is exported but divided into two files that are exported in separate processes. The order of the records in the two files is different so that the context of the records can be inferred. However, each record in these files contains a key (ID) that can be used to link and merge the records in both files. Furthermore, anonymisation of personal data is possible. For this purpose, the zone-related data is stored separately, as mentioned above, but the keys (ID) in the exported files are not included. An additional step for pseudonymisation or anonymisation of the data is therefore not necessary after the survey. The QUESTIONSTAR data protection and cookie policy can be found here:

<https://www.questionstar.de/hilfe/einstellungen-der-umfrage/datenschutz/>

4.1.2 Direct mailing (Month 6-48)

To avoid bombarding key stakeholders with information which might not be relevant to them, they will receive tailored information to capture and sustain their interest. This will also enhance interaction and engagement with them. A first mailout was sent to the project partners and the SBSM network to test the clarity of the content and the recipient's behavior when receiving this type of communication about the selected tools.

It is important to note that as the test subjects (recipients) must consent to the company's privacy policy no additional reference to privacy is included in this mailing. However, an accompanying note will be issued to the participants when the final mailing is produced. The following text has been sent to 206 individuals (see figure below).

This anonymous survey that was conducted and was also used for testing and to see if trends in content were already emerging.

Web-Ansicht | webview | Aperçu web | Vista Web | Visualizzazione web

Developing oxidoreductases for environment-friendly products

Dear Ms Hollmann,
My name is [redacted] and I am Principal Investigator in the project OXIPRO.
I am writing to you as you were mentioned to me by a colleague as a potential interested party in our project. Therefore, with this message I would like to cordially invite you to participate in our research project.

OXIPRO is a four-year initiative that aims to develop enzymes for environment-friendly, innovative, and sustainable consumer products for society.
To develop our products in a meaningful and sustainable manner, we want to identify the needs of future customers before developing our products.
Therefore we will use data-driven decision-making and co-creation to drive the innovation developed as part of the project. We will use our own data sources and experts to understand the needs, behaviours and motivations of our customers, but we are also dependent on and the feedback from future customers. This will help inform our project research activities and align them with your values and needs. Therefore we will identify our stakeholders opinions, requirements and expectations in relation to the products that we are developing.

As a stakeholder, you will be able to help guide development through joint activities and by engaging with us through the OXIPRO community.
We also like to offer you the opportunity to be involved in our project activities.
Participation can take place in form of surveys, round table talks and workshops. Participation in the project is voluntary. If you chose to participate, you can withdraw your consent at any time without giving a reason.

In the following you will have the opportunity to select and decide if and in which activities you participate in the future.
To receive the newsletter [click here](#).
Participation in [surveys](#) (Online)
Participation in [events](#) (workshops, round table talks, panel discussions)
If you prefer not to be contacted by OXIPRO, please [click here](#) and we will remove your e-mail-address.

Regardless of whether you decide to participate in our project activities, we would like to know which interest group you belong to. Therefore, we would be very pleased if you would participate in the following anonymous [survey](#). This survey takes less than a minute, but helps us to address our target group even more specifically.

Thank you for your cooperation!

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000607.

Abmeldenlink | unsubscribe | Lien de désinscription | Anular suscripción | Link di cancellazione

Results

The tool rapidmail enables us to observe the reading and clicking behavior of the recipients. The analysis of this was subsequently used to improve the text and design of the final mailout.

Out of 206 recipients 47,72 % (94) opened the email. 44 (22,34%) of them then clicked through. The click map showed:

35 (14.11%) followed the link to the OXIPRO webpage 35 (14.11%) followed the link to the newsletter

No one followed the link for registration in surveys or events 2 (1.2%) unsubscribed

37 (14.92%) followed the link to the survey 3 (1.21%) followed the link to Twitter

2 (0.8%) followed the link to LinkedIn

By analysing the click behavior of the recipients, we could then tailor the final email accordingly (see chapter 5).

The survey we linked to in the mailout was designed to enable us to learn from the respondents' feedback, optimise this knowledge for future surveys, and was 100% anonymous. Notice that this survey has been done with google forms as a tool. The prototype was created in Google forms for the test run, but the final version was produced using QUESTIONSTAR for the reasons described above.

The questions asked in the survey are presented here along with the corresponding answers

Can you tell us where you are from?

Spain	7
Germany	2
Italy	2
Other non EU country	1
Turkey	1
USA	1
Slovenia	1
UK	1
Answers:	16

Would you mind telling us your profession?

Microbiologist	1
Manager	2
Researcher	6
Chemist	2
Professor	2

NN	1
Engineer/biotechnologist	2
Answers:	16

What age group do you belong to?

Which of the following products most appeals to you?

Answers: 16

Theoretically, approximately 70 out of the 206 individuals who received the survey belong to the stakeholder groups «influencer» (high power, low interest) or «key player» (high interest, high power), according to the definition of priority groups per Mendelow [1] by virtue of their direct involvement and affiliation to the project. These individuals are «internal» stakeholders, and their engagement (positive or negative) has a direct impact on the project.

Who?	Reason to involve with OXIPRO, interest and benefits	Route	Work Package (WP) affected
OXIPRO executives, their administrations, Boards, EC	Management of OXIPRO (coordinating team, the Scientific Committee, the Management Committee, and the AB) and the EC. All wish to see the project succeed. They have additional communication requirements and need to be made aware of the project status so that they can decide what, if any, issues need to be escalated to the next executive level. Shareholders.	Internal	WP7 T7.1 WP8 T8.1, T8.5

The project members	Other projects such as e.g., the H2020 FNR-16 sister projects, local committees, and institutional boards such as e.g., faculty, institute, or work councils, labour unions. Some boards have a desire to maintain the standards in a certain area. Their power to stop the project can range from zero to full Identification of committees and boards that impact our activities. OXIPRO must consider their interest.	Internal	WP1 T1.1, T1.2, T1.3; WP7 T7.1, T7.2, T7.3, T7.4 WP8 T8.1, T8.5
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As only 16 individuals answered to the mailout, we considered that many project members are not aware of their power to influence project tasks. Although the survey was anonymous, all members of the project received the mail. The click rate could therefore have been significantly higher. When asked, it turned out that the members were not aware of their power to influence project tasks. We therefore inquired with some consortium members why they did not take part in the survey.

Conclusion

Some answered that they did not feel addressed as members of the project and saw it as information. Another group said that the mailing was too long and the text too detailed, requiring extensive reading time. This led to the message for the first survey being shortened and simplified accordingly (see Section 5). In order to better inform members about the survey, its motivation and content, a webinar on stakeholder engagement (persona modelling) was held as part of T1.2 (capacity building attachment) and a co-creation event (see 4.1.6) was held at the annual meeting in June 2022 to get members on board.

4.1.3 Newsletter (twice per year)

A periodic project eNewsletter is issued every six months to provide information on the project activities and developments. Each issue will be distributed via OXIPRO's dissemination channels.

To increase the outreach to potential stakeholders and to increase the impact of the surveys, a QR code was generated and embedded in the project newsletter. It is planned to include the QR code in the FNR-16 projects newsletter (Active Site).

To expand the list of contacts and participants, a QR code for surveys was also introduced, e.g., in the newsletters, in the partners' mailing list, via Twitter, etc. The QR code provides a simplified way to get information about OXIPRO and, if desired, links to register for future events.

The following QR code is an example of the QR code used to invite potential stakeholders to participate and subsequently categorise these participants. The QR code is accompanied by a short explanatory text:

You can be part of EU-funded OXIPRO Community! Would you like to work with the OXIPRO consortium and share your insights and thoughts with us? This way we can learn about your ideas and needs in terms of new, green enzyme-based products. By participating, you can help shape the development of the project through joint activities and by sharing your thoughts with us. Participation is voluntary and you can withdraw at any time. We guarantee that your data will be protected in accordance with the GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation). You can view our privacy policy [here](#). If you agree to the terms, please click on the QR code and take part in the 3-minute survey. This will allow us to tailor subsequent information and invitations to your exact interests and needs.

4.1.4 Round table talks (Year 1/3)

A multi-actor stakeholder group (comprising research, industry, and policy representatives) will be actively engaged through at least two round-table talks and at least two world cafés during the 1st and the 3rd years. Stakeholders will inform our understanding of the challenges of practical and technical implementation at institutional, administrative, and monetary levels and barriers that need to be overcome to enable OXIPRO's innovation transfer. One round-table talk will be organized with the multi-actor stakeholders and provide links with the project officer and policy officers. Another round-table talk will be organized as a joint policy meeting with the sister FNR-16 projects (Enxylascope, FuturEnzyme and Radicalz) and policymakers to agree on a harmonized form to deliver results for efficient feedback into policymaking. Findings from these discussions will be used to develop questions to be addressed in the world cafés and to inform research agenda roadmaps, feasibility studies and market replication analyses.

A first round-table talk was planned for June 2022 for the purpose of discussing the issue of “what hinders the implementation of LCA/CE in academic research streams and how to overcome these”. As also the persona modeling exercise in March and then more intensively in June 2022 demonstrate, the new products need to have a clear added value as “greener product”. Otherwise, the OXIPRO innovations would not be convincing alternatives on the market.

Approach

Two external experts were invited to use the opportunity to learn more about the prerequisites and practicalities LCA/circular economy principles for our project.

The following questions to the external experts were developed by SBSM and circulated to the partners for their feedback and approval prior to the planned event.

1. How can we measure the carbon footprint reduction that the use of OXIPRO products ensures?
2. While the environmental impact of the product per se is reduced using these novel enzymes, within OXIPRO we want to be sure that this innovation improvement is not achieved at the expense of increased CO₂ emissions during the production process. In our opinion, a new environmentally friendly product should generate a greener life cycle score compared to, for example, the chemical product it is intended to replace.
3. From your point of view, what are the key factors that we should consider for measuring our carbon footprint and the global environmental impact of the OXIPRO project?
4. How can we measure the difference in the life cycle between the OXIPRO process and the standard chemical one that it is replacing?
5. If this difference shows that the new life cycle is less efficient than the standard one, what can we do to decrease the environmental impact of our project?
6. The Carbon footprint is only one of the aspects that sustainable research should consider. It should also comply with circular economy principles that promote the reuse and recycling of existing materials and products.
7. As a specialist in new technologies based on biological processes, how do you think OXIPRO can implement circular economy strategies?
8. In particular, what are the possible decentralised processes for the upcycling of residual streams in the OXIPRO project?
9. Second-generation bio-based products are one of the pillars of the circular economy principles. For example, bio-based plastics have the potential to become sustainable alternatives to petrochemical-based plastics.
10. We also were interested in learning if participants are interested in bio-based products from second generation lignocellulosics, such as fibre and materials. Therefore, the following questions have been addressed:
11. From your point of view, what can OXIPRO do to contribute to these second- generation bio-based products?
12. Can you provide us with an example for better understanding this process, maybe using our home textile products as the starting point for creating second-generation bio-based products
13. After the agreement on the questions, SBSM started to advertise the event and sent multiple emails and messages via teams with calls for registration to the partners: In addition to the mailing, a flyer was developed and uploaded to twitter and LinkedIn for advertising the event.

REGISTRATION

STAKEHOLDER EVENT OXIPRO 2022

Participation is free of any fees. Refreshments are included. However, Participation is **limited to 20 participants**. To register, send mail to hello@oxipro.eu with subject line „Registration Stakeholder meeting“

Please register until **May 25, 2022**

Venue: Conference and meeting centre Het Kasteel
Het Kasteel (57)
Melkweg 1, 9718 EP Groningen

From Groningen Central Station:
City bus line 6 (Vinkhuizen) or **line 9** (towards Station Noord – Zernike)
Alight at the stop 'Verlengde Visserstraat/Westersingel'.

Source: <https://www.google.com/maps>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000607

INVITATION

Stakeholder Meeting

Transition towards environment-friendly consumer products by co-creation of an oxidoreductase foundry

June 8
10 am to 12 am, 2022
Groningen, The Netherlands

How to facilitate sustainable research and innovation transfer from research into application?

Everybody is talking about circular economy and innovation transfer. Both, important drivers of the European strategy to optimise the impact and exploitation of knowledge and ideas.

Background is to making research results more efficient science, as well as to innovation in public and private sectors. Hence, in order to derive maximum benefit from research not only skills in the development process but also properly knowledge and analysis of the values, cost benefit analysis and regulatory factors, international climate agreements, new customer requirements and market initiatives for future products.

To achieve this, we need training, procedures as well as workflows that enable the implementation of these aspects in the R&D process. Currently, there is a lack of experts who understand the principles and possess knowledge of these principles in the context of academic research flows. This is a major barrier hindering the implementation of sustainability and thus circular economy in academic research. Major reason for this is an insufficient and unequal education of scientists in life science that is inherently varied, complex in nature, and large in volume. Within the OXIPRO will cooperate with experts to develop new solutions with a focus on the sustainability of our future products. The aim of the event is to learn from the different perspectives, share experiences and needs in order to find possible solutions on how to improve our efforts in the holistic context of OXIPRO. This discussion will help us in our work, especially in developing sustainable products.

We expect participants to have a fruitful discussion that will improve mutual understanding and help us to consider and respect aspects of other stakeholders in our future activities.

Within the stakeholder meeting we invite you to experience the view of the other side(s) and to enter in a discussion with each other.

This event consists of two parts: First, participants will be welcomed by the coordinator and given a short introduction to OXIPRO and its future products. This is followed by several short presentations by representatives of the circular economy in which the causes of the existing problems in connection with the circular economy are presented from their point of view. Ideally, there will be a direct connection with our products. In the second session, we will have an open discussion focusing on the questions and needs arising from the results of the first session.

AGENDA	
10:00	Welcome address by the chair of the Action Dr. Gro Ejeriga Short presentation of OXIPRO
10:15	Pitch presentations by <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Joeren Tideman (Bioclear earth b.v.) • Sara Campesano (Hedgehog Company) • tba
11:00	Discussion / exchange & round table talk
11:45	Closing remarks
12:00	End of event

"We take you on a journey behind the scenes and invite you to look at the topic through the eyes of various stakeholders."

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000607

Result

Due to a disappointingly small number of registrations for the stakeholder event on circular economy and life cycle assessment (2 registrants vs 5 organisers) this event could not take place.

Another round table talk is planned for spring 2023.

Conclusion

The partners did not understand what the event was about and that their cooperation was needed. They do not see themselves as stakeholders and therefore did not feel addressed. SBSM then sent an explanatory email to the partners with information and explanations and the promotion of the event, unfortunately without success.

4.1.5 World Café (Year 1/3)

The world café provides a space where participants can get to know each other's different perspectives, discover different approaches to a topic, learn new forms of interaction, listen carefully, question, and discuss. Within this environment, multiple stakeholders can congregate and discuss identified inefficiencies and develop co-creative solutions towards the delivery of targeted innovation-led solutions.

Approach

A world café typically lasts between 45 minutes and three hours. Participants gather in small groups round a table. Meanwhile, 'Moderators' field appropriate questions and engage people in constructive dialogue ensuring the linking of the findings from the different discussion sessions. In the course of this process, two or three different questions are discussed in successive sessions of 15 to 30 minutes at all tables. Participants move from table to table while moderator stay in one location). The event concludes with a reflection phase. While one world café will take place with representatives of business/industry and consumer associations, another can be open for a broader spectrum of participants, targeting the potential end-users. Outcomes of the world cafés will identify core questions to be processed in co-creation workshops with members of the consortium.

Result

As the stakeholder mapping was delayed due to the requirement to implement WP9 and its related GDPR settings (more specific data transfer arrangements), the stakeholder identification approach was delayed. The world café has been postponed to Spring2023.

4.1.6 Co-Creation (Year 1/3)

The first co-creation event took place at the annual meeting in Groningen and focused on persona modelling. The purpose of this was to raise awareness and enhance understanding of stakeholder

identification and engagement activities. The consortium came together for the joint processing of research questions related to OXIPRO's enzyme targets, product applications, value chains, and customer values and desires. Outcomes of this, including four specification sheets on enzyme, process, and product requirements for each of the innovation cases, were collected to feed into work in WP2-WP6 and will be continuously updated.

In the implementation of this event, a session was implemented in which the members of the consortium were divided into 4 groups (according to the 4 innovation cases of OXIPRO). In order to get the greatest possible mix of participants, the formation of groups was achieved by offering four different sweets choices to assign themselves to a certain group before the session. One topic (group) was assigned to each sweet and the participants were grouped according to their choice. (Figure slide 1).

In the next step the groups were asked to identify potential stakeholders and place them on a graph, thereby assigning them different powers and interest in the topic in accordance to Mendelow's matrix approach (Figure slide 4).

The diagram titled "Identify Stakeholders" outlines a three-step process for stakeholder identification. Step 1 involves creating a list of 20 stakeholders on a post-it. Step 2 involves organizing these stakeholders on a two-dimensional graph based on power and interest. Step 3 involves analyzing the priority of each stakeholder. The graph is a 2x2 matrix with "Level of power" on the y-axis (Low to High) and "Level of interest" on the x-axis (Low to High). The quadrants are labeled: Key Players (High Power, High Interest), Influencers (High Power, Low Interest), Interested (Low Power, High Interest), and Passive (Low Power, Low Interest). The OXIPRO logo is in the top right corner, and a small "4" is in the bottom right corner.

Step 1: Create a list of 20 possible stakeholders and write each of them on a post-it. M W U S T < O

Step 2: Organise the stakeholders on the two-dimensional graph qualifying them with an amount of power and interest between „low“ or „high“

Step 3: Analyse the priority of each stakeholder and identify those who are strategic due to their importance.

In the next step, participants selected two personas from the list of potential stakeholders: one persona with low interest but high power and a second persona with high power and high interest. For each persona, the groups discussed and collected aspects of needs, interests, fears and potential inhibitors in context with the topic (Figure slide5).

Create your persona Poster 2

Step 4: Split group in two subgroups: **subgroup 1** create a persona which has low interest but high-power **subgroup 2** create a persona with high interest and high power.

Collect aspects of needs, interest, fears, **potential inhibitors** etc. for both in context with the topic.

In the next step, group members discussed measures on how to convince the persona with low interest to become a persona with high interest and vice versa (Figure slide 6) to reflect on the personas created with their attitudes, values and desires, but also on potentially relevant measures for their engagement.

Convince the person from the other field to come to yours

Step 5: Appoint a representative from your group. Go into confrontation with the other stakeholder and try to convince him/her to change from pro to con and vice versa.

Develop a strategy

Step 6: Merge the subgroups and discussing your experiences from the discussion. What was good? What did not work? What could have been done better?

Develop a strategy on how best to translate this experience and aspects into communication actions to keep potential stakeholders from the two groups informed or involved.

Step 7: Expand the strategy to all groups. The strategy can define the stakeholders involved in the process, the needs of each stakeholder, who each stakeholder will involve in the project, and any aspects related to involving individuals or collectives.

A strategy on “how to” was developed within the groups and presented to the whole auditorium. (Figure slide 7). This formed the basis for discussion on stakeholder engagement activities (Figure slide 8).

Step 8: Present your results

Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4

Approach

Participants comprised the members of the OXIPRO consortium who were participating in the OXIPRO annual meeting in Groningen, NL. They were divided into four groups to work on the stakeholder mapping and persona modelling.

The first step in the persona modelling process was the mapping of potentially relevant stakeholders. The task was first to collect as many stakeholder groups as possible, and then identify their positioning in the matrix of “interest” and “power”. Stakeholders identified with “high power, high interest” from all discussion groups were:

On the producer/industry side

- Investors
- Suppliers
- Manufacturers, enzyme producers, detergent/pharmaceutical/textile/beauty/dietary supplement/pet food industry
- Retailers
- Lobbyists

On societal side

- Policy makers
- Regulators
- NGOs, environmental organisations
- (social) media

On the consumer side

- consumers with values
- athletes
- parents

The next step was to select a persona representing one of the identified stakeholder groups and develop a detailed picture of the person including their interests/hobbies/values, how and when they would use the products conceive potential expectations towards the new product and identify potential inhibitors.

Results

Overall, expectations included the performance of the new product, the handling, benefits and added value, the advantage of the new product compared to the existing competing products, and the match with personal values (for “greener” products).

The persona modelling also revealed as potential inhibitors

- competing existing products
- price
- difficulty to change consumer habits
- packaging
- accessibility
- regulatory barriers
- concerns about genetically modified organisms
- compatibility with existing infrastructure (e.g., washing machines, production pipelines)

Results from the group work on stakeholder mapping

Results from the group work on selected personas

Name **MARY**
 Age **40**
 Profession **EDUCATOR**
 Family status **FAMILY w/CHILDREN**
 Quote

CONSUMER

- FAMILY TIME
- ENVIRONMENT
- CLIMATE CHANGES
- HEALTHY LIVING
- SPORTS

- MORE ENV. FRIENDLY
- MORE EFFICIENT
- KEEPS CLOTHES IN BETTER CONDITIONS
- CLEAN MORE FASTER
- CLEAN AT LOWER T (°C)
- LESS CHEMICALS
- EASY TO USE

#Interests#Hobbies#Values
WEEKLY/DAILY USE

#Expectations towards the new product

- COST
- POOR PRODUCT
- NOT USER FRIENDLY
- NOT COMPATIBLE w/ WASHING EQUIPMENT (MACHINE)

Name **MARY**
 Age **40**
 Profession **EDUCATOR**
 Family status **FAMILY w/CHILDREN**
 Quote

CONSUMER

- FAMILY TIME
- ENVIRONMENT
- CLIMATE CHANGES
- HEALTHY LIVING
- SPORTS

- MORE ENV. FRIENDLY
- MORE EFFICIENT
- KEEPS CLOTHES IN BETTER CONDITIONS
- CLEAN MORE FASTER
- CLEAN AT LOWER T (°C)
- LESS CHEMICALS
- EASY TO USE

#Interests#Hobbies#Values
WEEKLY/DAILY USE

#Expectations towards the new product

- COST
- POOR PRODUCT
- NOT USER FRIENDLY
- NOT COMPATIBLE w/ WASHING EQUIPMENT (MACHINE)

OXIPRO

Name **AXEL**
 Age **29**
 Profession **MARKETING DIRECTOR**
 Family status **IN RELATIONSHIP (TWO HAVE 3 DOGS TOO)**
 Quote **ADVERTISING IS USE JUNKY BUT, BRANDING IS USE HUBBIE**

MARKETING

FIT GAS
ENHANCING SPEEDS
BRANDING
EXTENSIVE SELF-AWARENESS

BRAND EQUITY ↑
EXTRA CLAIMS/BOOKS
COST EFFECTIVE
FIT TO BRAND EFFY
TOP PERFORMANCE
PERCEIVED BENEFIT
EXCLUSIVITY

(How they perceive what you claim you do)

#Interests#Hobbies#Values
IN FRONT LEADER WASHING MACHINE
WASHES A WEEK
WASHES EXCESSIVE CLOTHING
AT LEAST TWICE
↳ EVERYONE WASHES
↳ EVERYONE WASHES CLOTHES
*** WOULD BE HAPPY TO SWITCH TO NEW CLOTHES**

#Expectations towards the new product

- COMPETITORS
- PRICE
- REVIEWER ACCEPTANCE
- CONSUMER INSIGHTS
- CONSUMER HABITS
- FORMAT (PRODUCT)
- PACKAGING
- ↳ TO
- GEOGRAPHY
- MACHINE HANDLING (CONSUMER)

#How and when using the product

#Potential inhibitors

OXIPRO
 Name: PANOS
 Age: 36-42
 Profession: Innovation director
 Family status: Married with two children and a baby
 Quote: "Clean family & environment"

Interests/Hobbies/Values
 Outdoor basketball
 Sailing and fishing
 Family life
 Environmental concerns

Expectations towards the new product
 Eco-friendly
 Easy & > Jumbo packs!
 Cheap
 Uses to use "a lot"
 Properly cleaned also on "short cycles" → efficiency.
 "Germ-free" washing
 ↳ no pathogens (sanitization)

How and when using the product
 After heavy training, not after a light gym session.
 Daily for kids' clothes
 Twice, short wash for baby
 Evening & night routine → when energy is cheaper.
 Nice smells of "ocean breeze" and fresh clothes

Potential inhibitors
 Willingness to pay (cost low)
 Green-washing (profit "more green")
 Time! Efficiency is important.
 Smell, could be too much, or too little.
 Disagreement in family

OXIPRO
 Name: JOANNE
 Age: 36
 Profession: sustainability officer
 Family status: Single
 Quote:

Interests/Hobbies/Values
 Fashion (responsible)
 Durability
 Hiking
 Horse riding
 Camping
 Busy city life + lots of travels

Expectations towards the new product
 Effective
 Low material impact
 Preserve fabric and color
 Strong marketing partner

How and when using the product
 At home / personal use
 Testing effect on fabrics at work.
 During her trips

Potential inhibitors
 Cost
 Effectiveness
 Accessibility
 Reliability of claims
 Company culture

OXIPRO
 Name: John Doe the 3rd
 Age: 64
 Profession: Financial Mgr. of Environment (Fr.)
 Family status: Married 2nd wife, 2 child 1st marriage
 Quote: "By Government Subsidy By Producers"

Interests/Hobbies/Values
 ↳ Wine connoisseur
 ↳ Sailing
 ↳ Reading
 ↳ Volunteering / Public passion
 ↳ Co-owner Restaurant Tradition Branch
 ↳ Well Networked
 ↳ Community Garden

Expectations towards the new product
 Green Product
 Concerned with LCE
 Concerned About GMO'S
 Removal of Fish Smell
 Unique solution
 Expects Support From the Industry

How and when using the product
 Wants Consumer Perspective
 Sustainable Package
 Value chain
 ↳ Life cycle etc.

Potential inhibitors
 Does not understand the complete Science
 Afraid of GMO'S
 is it Moral to patent a Gene / Enzyme?
 Shaky legal foundation

OXIPRO
 Name: KAMILIA GARCIA
 Age: 45
 Profession: HEAD BUSINESS DEV / VALORIZATION
 Family status: MARRIED (2 KIDS) / 10, 18
 Quote: "LET'S DO IT RIGHT"

Interests/Hobbies/Values
 YOGA (FREE YOGA MAT)
 NATURE
 WORK/LIFE
 CAREER
 ↳ EASY TO
 ↳ LUNCH MEETINGS APPROACH?
 PLOT PROJECT FOR FREE
 TAILORED (LCA) MARKET

Expectations towards the new product
 ENVIRONMENTAL
 \$\$\$
 ADDED VALUE
 IMAGE (Log green)
 CHANGE
 VIDEO/MARKETING

How and when using the product
 EXPANSION → Adding Value
 TEST PROTOTYPING
 ASAP

Potential inhibitors
 TIME → MAKE IT SIMPLE
 COST (- PRODUCT ITSELF
 (- FACILITIES
 REGULATION
 TOO SCIENCE?

Conclusion

From the discussions and presentations about the stakeholder mapping and persona modelling also some general conclusions could be drawn:

Overall, the OXIPRO claims must be carefully and specifically defined. The claims must be clear and convincing to all relevant stakeholder groups that have been identified. Often, the communication about advantages of the new OXIPRO products are still too scientific, and especially non-experts need to be addressed in non-specialist language that is comprehensible to a broad range of stakeholder groups. Also, potentially existing conflicts of interest need to be identified; communication measures need to be adapted to these potential conflicts and fears that might exist in the population and for specific stakeholder groups.

An incisive Life Cycle Assessment is necessary to support the messages on the new OXIPRO products. The carbon footprints of the new products need to be at least competitive with the existing products, so that in the best case we can demonstrate that the new OXIPRO products are advantageous in terms of a reduced environmental burden.

Interviews and surveys with the relevant stakeholder groups are a means of identifying potential conflicts of interest, needs, values, attitudes, preferences, and relevant barriers. This can also be achieved also with representatives of the stakeholders in focus groups.

Dissemination measures are necessary to specifically target consumers. Social media platforms provide effective opportunities to communicate directly or indirectly with consumers and inform them about the new OXIPRO approaches and products. Additionally, the group discussion revealed that direct contact with consumers might be effective in addition to media activities.

It might be significant to allow consumers to test the products hands-on to trial and measure their performance and compatibility with needs, habits, and user-friendliness within a given environment (e.g., washing machine).

If in some cases a direct contact with the relevant stakeholder groups cannot be made may be necessary to develop strategies for indirect contact, e.g., via influencers or lobbyists.

4.1.7 Consortium meetings (annually)

Key stakeholders (and influencers) could be invited to consortium meeting for consultation to facilitate engagement and learning from the process

The first annual meeting was a closed event. However, members of the AB participated to provide input and feedback to the research activities.

4.1.8 Delphi survey (Year 3)

Identification of potential educational, cultural, gender- or generation derived issues will be actioned

through a Delphi survey to transform opinion into group consensus regarding the end users view of production (e.g., biotechnology for tailormade applications), consumption habits, adoption or rejection or use of the results/products. Outcomes will be considered for internal use (responsiveness) and will also be used to generate a catalogue of recommendations to address aspects in future exploitation measures (T.1.3). Information will also feed into a social impact assessment (WP6).

4.1.9 Direct personal exchange “Meet a Scientist” (Year 3)

In the 3rd year, OXIPRO will run two “Meet a Scientist” events during European Biotech Week to establish relationships between researchers, scientists and community members and thereby foster dialogue and trust.

4.2 Data protection

D1.3 is also closely linked to D9.1 and D9.4 (WP Ethics) because it gathers personal data (names, contact details of the stakeholders) and thus needs to follow data management requirements of GDPR. All activities require compliance with the rules agreed on in WP9, with its deliverables concerning ethical requirements during the collection, storage, and processing of personal information. For the implementation of the surveys, it is necessary to work with tools that meet the requirements of data protection. The collection and analysis of data will be performed in a secured environment within SBSM’s own highly secure cloud. Access to data will be restricted to those consortium partners who are dependent on the information to complete their tasks and/or deliverables, and who have signed the data transfer agreement (DTA) for outgoing data. For the collection of data, SBSM/NORCE will share a DTA for incoming data to be signed by both parties before data collection.

A mailing list resulting from the analysis will be managed by SBSM/NORCE to ensure that individuals who are on the lists will not be identifiable by third parties.

The individual tasks and procedures to collect data are detailed in the ethics deliverable

D9.1.(Confidential)

A short summary is given here:

Data Protection:

The data controller for personal data collected is: Name: SBSM

Postal address:

SB Science Management UG (haftungsbeschränkt) Muthesiusstr.11
12163 Berlin - Germany Phone. +493063228660

E-mail: datenschutz@sb-sciencemanagement.com.

Data Protection Officer (DPO) is [REDACTED]. If you have any questions about this privacy notice, please contact the data controller using contact information above.

Statistical survey of interest and commitment to the objectives of OXIPRO. Participation is voluntary. By participating in the survey, you consent to the processing of your survey data. The collected data

will be treated strictly confidential. The evaluation of the data is pseudonymous and aggregated.

Your rights:

You may assert a claim based on the right to information, to rectification, erasure or blocking, restriction or objection of data processing and data portability (Art.15-21 GDPR) against **{contact datenschutz[at]sb-sciencemanagement.com}**, if there is a personal reference. For this survey, you can object to the data processing of your personal data at any time to **{contact survey[at]sb-sciencemanagement.com}**.

You can unsubscribe from our survey invitations at any time by replying to this email and entering "UNSUBSCRIBE" in the subject line or clicking the unsubscribe link.

What data will be included?

Any information related to the diversity of participants and their interest and engagement that will help partners meet future needs of the project. (***Gender, Age, Profession, Country of residence***)

Non-sharing of data

There will be NO sharing of email addresses with third parties. Email addresses will only be used for survey invitations.

The detailed data privacy policy for the measures of surveys / questionnaires can be found here:

<https://sb-sciencemanagement.com/datenschutz>

4.3 Survey

Maximising OXIPRO's impact requires a clear understanding of the interests and influence of the stakeholders and a strategy to address their needs. The first step is the identification of the stakeholders. To this end, we asked the project partners which entities they consider as having an interest in or influence on the project's outcomes. They also confirmed whether they could be referred to as the initial contact and classified their suggested entities according to their expected levels of interest and influence. As a result of this process, 419 individuals and entities were identified. The mailout was created to establish initial contact in order to inform about OXIPRO, and to invite them to contribute as stakeholders. In compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the Data Transfer Agreement, we asked for their consent and invited them to respond to the survey with the option to register or withdraw. The survey was fundamental to establishing who the stakeholders are and positioning them within a matrix of interest and influence based on their self-perception.

1. To comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the team used **rapidmail** (<https://www.rapidmail.de/>) to establish the first contact with the multi-actor stakeholder group. Below we present both the text and the image of the mailout received, which comprise: An overview of the project and its main goals
2. An invitation to participate as a stakeholder
3. Clarification regarding the voluntary nature of the participation and the data protection
4. The link to the OXIPRO Privacy and Data Policy
5. The link to the survey, hosted on Question Star(<https://www.questionstar.de/>).
6. Two different options: to subscribe to or withdraw
7. The project logo and EU funding acknowledgement.

Email text:

Dear (Name),

The team at SB Science Management is contacting you as you have been identified as a fundamental stakeholder for our current EU-funded project **OXIPRO**. OXIPRO is a four-year initiative that **aims to develop enzymes for environment-friendly, innovative, and sustainable consumer products for society**. We would like to invite you to collaborate by providing us with your insights and enabling us to learn about your perceptions and needs regarding new enzyme-based, greener products. As a stakeholder, you can help guide the project's development through joint activities and by engaging with us through the OXIPRO community. Your participation can take place in the form of surveys, round table talks, and workshops.

Participation is voluntary, and you can withdraw at any time. We guarantee that your data is protected in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). You can access our privacy and data policy [here](#).

If you agree with the terms, please click [here](#) and proceed to the button below. This will launch a 3-minute survey which will help us accurately tailor subsequent information and invitations to your interests and requirements.

Thank you in advance for your cooperation. We are excited to welcome you to the OXIPRO community!

In accordance with instructions from the partners, we divided the mailouts between those who authorized the identification of the initial contact and those who did not. In total, 419 emails were sent. Of these, 57 bounced and 362 were delivered. One week later, a follow-up e-mail was sent to recipients who had not opened the first email. According to the statistics provided by the rapidmail platform, 231 e-mails were opened.

Developing oxidoreductases
for environment-friendly products

Dear Max,

The team at SB Science Management is contacting you as you have been identified as a fundamental stakeholder for our current EU-funded project **OXIPRO**. OXIPRO is a four-year initiative that **aims to develop enzymes for environment-friendly, innovative, and sustainable consumer products for society**.

We would like to invite you to collaborate by providing us with your insights and enabling us to learn about your perceptions and needs regarding new enzyme-based, greener products. As a stakeholder, you can help guide the project's development through joint activities and by engaging with us through the OXIPRO community. Your participation can take place in the form of surveys, round table talks, and workshops.

Participation is voluntary, and you can withdraw at any time. We guarantee that your data is protected in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). You can access our privacy and data policy [here](#).

If you agree with the terms, please click [here](#) and proceed to the button below. This will launch a 3-minute survey which will help us accurately tailor subsequent information and invitations to your interests and requirements.

Thank you in advance for your cooperation. We are excited to welcome you to the OXIPRO community!

[SURVEY](#)

If you prefer not to be contacted by OXIPRO, please click [here](#), and we will remove your e-mail address.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000607.

Follow OXIPRO on Twitter or LinkedIn:

[Click here to unsubscribe from the mailing list.](#)

Approach

The Survey

Considering the concept of stakeholder adopted and the task of categorize them according to their area, interest and influence on the project, the questions were elaborated. Those Stakeholders consist of people indicated by the partners and understood as individuals, groups or organisations who are directly or indirectly affected by OXIPRO's activities or who have an interest in OXIPRO's activities and /or outcomes or who are relevant for the projects progress and success.

In the following, the material generated and the results of the survey are presented.

Dear Stakeholder,

Welcome to OXIPRO Community! **OXIPRO** is a four-year initiative that is developing enzymes for environment-friendly, innovative, and sustainable consumer products for society.

The processes and products we are developing concern particularly the textiles, detergents, nutraceuticals, and cosmetics industries.

To drive innovation within OXIPRO and to develop our products in a meaningful and sustainable manner, we are identifying the needs and perspectives of our stakeholders beforehand using data-driven decision-making and co-creation strategies, such as this survey.

This survey comprises four short questions. The information you kindly provide will enable us to tailor subsequent surveys and invitations to events in accordance with your interests. With your participation

Please provide your email address (Notice: your data is needed to assign follow-up activities to you. Your data are protected according to GDPR and will only be used for internal purposes)

Question 1/4

I am

- a researcher
- a policymaker
- an industry representative
- a product developer
- a consumer representative
- a consumer
- a housewife / a househusband
- Other

Question 2/4

I work

- in Research and Development
- in academia
- in a regulatory or legislative body
- in government
- in public services
- in the textile industry
- in the detergents industry
- in the nutraceuticals industry
- in the cosmetics industry
- as a lobbyist
- in a non-governmental organisation
- Other

Question 3/4

As stated above, OXIPRO is a four-year initiative that is developing enzymes for environment-friendly, innovative, and sustainable consumer products for society. Within this framework, how do you assess your interest and influence in relation to the following aspects?

	Low	Medium	High
Your interest in researching and developing sustainable consumer products for society.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Your influence on political decision-makers with regard to OXIPRO's developments and products at national level.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Your influence on political decision-makers with regard to OXIPRO's developments and products at international level.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Your influence on consumer rights for future OXIPRO products at national level.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Your influence on consumer rights for future OXIPRO products at international level.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Your influence on the consumer products industry.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Your interest in sustainable consumer products for society.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Your influence on the consumption behaviour of OXIPRO products.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Question 4/4 (please select all those that are applicable)

I am interested in participating in

- Workshops
- Roundtables and panel discussions
- Surveys
- Research-related events
- Policy-related events
- Industry-related events
- Consumer-related events

Thank you for your time and input. We will get back to you soon.**Data Protection:**

The data controller for personal data collected within this survey is:

Name: SB Science Management UG (haftungsbeschränkt) - SBSM

Postal address:

SB Science Management UG (haftungsbeschränkt)

Muthesiusstr.11

12163 Berlin - Germany

Phone: +493063228660

Email: E-mail: [datenschutz\[at\]sb-sciencemanagement.com](mailto:datenschutz[at]sb-sciencemanagement.com).Data Protection Officer (DPO) is Susanne Hollmann. If you have any questions about this privacy notice (<https://sb-sciencemanagement.com/imprint>) please contact the data controller using contact information above.**Purpose of survey and processing of survey data:**

Statistical survey of interest and commitment to the objectives of OXIPRO. Participation is voluntary. By participating in the survey, you consent to the processing of your survey data. The collected data will be treated strictly confidential. The evaluation of the data is pseudonymous and aggregated.

Your rights:You may assert a claim based on the right to information, to rectification, erasure or blocking, restriction or objection of data processing and data portability (Art. 15-21 GDPR) against ([contact datenschutz\[at\]sb-sciencemanagement.com](mailto:contact_datenschutz[at]sb-sciencemanagement.com)), provided that there is a personal reference. For this survey, you can object to the data processing of your personal data at any time to ([contact survey\[at\]sb-sciencemanagement.com](mailto:contact_survey[at]sb-sciencemanagement.com)).

You can unsubscribe from our survey invitations at any time by email and entering "UNSUBSCRIBE" in the subject line or clicking the unsubscribe link if provided.

What data will be included?Any information related to the diversity of participants and their interest and engagement that will help partners meet future needs of the project. (**Gender, Age, Profession, Country of residence**)**Non-sharing of data**

There will be NO sharing of email addresses with third parties. Email addresses will only be used for survey invitations.

Results

- The survey was started by 45 recipients and completed by 38. We then analysed the results obtained from each question and categorised them as follows: Stakeholder identification
- Stakeholders' working area
- Stakeholders' level of influence and interest
- Stakeholders' involvement with the project

QUESTION 1- Stakeholders' Identification

- I am

Among others we find

Answers	Respondents	Percent
project manager	1	25,0%
Professor	1	25,0%
academician	1	25,0%
Product & Service Promoter	1	25,0%
Total	4	100,0%

QUESTION 2- Stakeholders' Working Area

I work

In total, 14 E-mail campaigns were sent

QUESTION 3- Stakeholders' level of influence and interest

Considering that OXIPRO project is a four-year initiative that aims to develop enzymes for environment-friendly, innovative, and sustainable consumer products for society. How do you rate?

Interest

Influence

QUESTION 4- Stakeholders' involvement in the project I am interested in participating in

From the data analysis, we identified the respondents' locations and field/sector of interest. This enabled us to proceed with the stakeholder mapping

Countries

Areas

Finally, using their stated areas of interest and influence, the stakeholders were classified within a power vs interest grid produced by Eden and Ackermann (1998) [2]. Of the 38 participants 32 external

e-mails and analysed their answers regarding their perceived levels of influence and interest.

Stakeholder quadrant

Source: www.stakeholder.map [3]

Position	Area	Level of Influence	Level of Interest	Classification- Analysis
Product & Service	Research & Development	low	high	show consideration
Researcher	Research & Development	high	high	Key Player
Industry Representative	Industry-Business	low	high	show consideration
Industry Representative	Industry-Business	low	medium	show consideration
Industry Representative	Industry-Business	low	high	show consideration
Industry Representative	Research & Development	low	high	show consideration
Researcher	Research & Development	low	high	show consideration
Researcher	Research & Development	medium	high	Key Player
Researcher	Academia	medium	medium	show consideration
Researcher	Academia	medium	low	show consideration
Researcher	Academia	low	high	show consideration
Researcher	Academia	high	high	Key Player
Researcher	Research & Development	low	high	show consideration
Industry Representative	Research & Development	low	high	show consideration
Industry Representative	Public Services	low	medium	show consideration
Researcher	Academia	low	medium	show consideration
Researcher	Research & Development	medium	high	Key Player
Researcher	Academia	low	high	show consideration
Researcher	Academia	medium	high	Key Player
Professor	Academia	low	high	show consideration
Researcher	Research & Development	low	high	show consideration
Researcher	Research & Development	low	high	show consideration
Consumer	Society	low	low	least important
Researcher	Academia	low	high	show consideration
Researcher	Academia	low	high	show consideration
Researcher	Academia	medium	medium	show consideration
Industry Representative	Research & Development	low	medium	show consideration
Researcher	Academia	medium	medium	show consideration
Researcher	Academia	low	high	show consideration
Industry Representative	Research & Development	medium	high	Key Player
Product & Service	Industry-Business	Low	High	show consideration

Conclusion

The above table illustrates part of the process as to keep personal information confidential. The data shows that the majority of stakeholders come from Research and Industry and have a high level of interest, but a low level of influence on policy and consumer behavior or rights. We inferred that direct contact from referring partner may have facilitated a higher degree of response from the respective stakeholder(s). Considering the importance of expanding this list, the final step entailed establishing a shortlist of those considered the most influential stakeholders. Contact providing partners were therefore asked to get in direct contact with the stakeholder in order to motivate them to participate in the survey.

5 Attachments

5.1 Webinars

Persona modelling

A webinar was held in March 2022 to inform, engage and commitment the team. As the partners are considered as key players for the success of the project their commitment to the activities is mandatory. Therefore, a webinar was held to inform about the planned activities, methodologies and about the importance of the contributions of the project partners.

«Dear all,

please do not forget our date for the next lecture in our lecture series. This week (Wednesday, March 16 at 3:30 pm) we will be dealing with the topic of "**stakeholder engagement**". After a short introduction to the topic of **design thinking**, we will create **personas** in small groups. As archetypal users, personas represent the objectives and needs of the target group and enable us to make informed decisions in the development of user-friendly products right from the start. We hope for lively participation. »

16 members including the organisers participated in this training session. This showed again that the interest of internal stakeholders is rather low. Therefore, a co-creation event at the annual meeting in June 2022 took place to further work on the consortium's commitment to understanding and engaging with stakeholders.

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Persona Modeling

- > What is design thinking?
- > Introduction to Persona Modeling
- > Group work: Developing your persona
- > Customer Journey Mapping

“To create meaningful innovations, you need to know your users and care about their lives”.

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Typical design process

Converge

Conventional business practice vs. Design Thinking approach

<http://de.slideshare.net/ucyc4e/ideo-design-thinking-workshop-2016>

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Design as non-linear process

Converge

Diverge & Converge

Conventional business practice vs. Design Thinking approach

<http://de.slideshare.net/ucyc4e/ideo-design-thinking-workshop-2016>

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EMPATHISE

Empathise Define Ideas Prototype Test

Empathise:
When you feel what the other person is feeling and can mirror their expression, their opinions, and their hopes

Why?
To discover people's explicit and implicit needs so that they can meet them through your design solutions

Hasso Plattner Institute of Design Thinking

OXIPRO

EMPATHISE

It is impossible to define a key challenge or product for everyone!

Empathise Define Ideas Prototype Test

<https://scripte.matthias-edler-golla.de/sose19/interface-design/personas-scenarios>

OXIPRO

Persona Modeling

Empathise Define Ideas Prototype Test

Personas are **fictional characters**, which you create in order to represent the **different user types** that might use your service, product, site, or brand in a similar way.

Personas make the design task less complex, they **guide your ideation processes**, and they can help you to achieve the goal of creating a good user experience for your target user group.

<https://www.interaction-design.org/literature/article/personas-why-and-how-you-should-use-them>

Persona Modeling

Persona

Typical quote

Name: Age Profession
 Living conditions / Family / daily routine

Interests, values

Leisure time activities

Problems

Wishes, desires

- name, age, defined lifestyle and workstyle, leisure time
- key attributes that might affect use and expectations of the product or service...
- frequently performed tasks
- problems, pain points
- interests, wishes
- a catchphrase that distinguishes the persona from others
-

CREATE A PERSONA

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PERSONA MODELLING

Persona

Typical quote

Name: Age Profession
 Living conditions / Family / daily routine

Interests, values

Leisure time activities

Problems

Wishes, desires

Family and social status, social group, tradition, income, region, time limitations

Health, sustainability, regionality, transparency, accessibility of products,

Conflicts: Tradition vs. innovations, sustainability vs. price, reusability

More leisure time activities vs. time for household, Peer group orientation

Safe the world, circular economy, good life with less efforts, more leisure time, access to luxury goods

Customer Journey Mapping

Touchpoints: which steps/phases does the persona undergo on the journey? Define user actions for each step/phase

Needs, frustrations: which needs, frustrations, problems does the persona experience during the journey?

Emotions, feelings: which feelings does the persona have at each step of the journey?

Improvements for experience: which experiences should be made/ are expected to be made at each step? Which improvements are needed?

Ideas to realise improvements: how can the experience be improved?

Idea Napkin

Description of the use/activity („journey“):

	Phase 1	Phase 2	Phase 3	Phase 4
Touchpoints:				
Needs, frustrations:				
Emotions, feelings:				
Description of ideal experience:				
Ideas to realise improvements:				

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Customer Journey Mapping

Things to observe:

- Behaviours that people do over and over again throughout the day
- Dynamics and interactions between people
- Quirky workarounds

Main question **WHY?**

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Thank you very much for your attention and active participation in the discussion!

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SB Science Management UG

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Cappucino talks

WP1

Core Group:
 SBSM
NORCE
LEITAT
REDINN

Task 1.1 Stakeholder identification & engagement

Stakeholders from x x x x

Co-Creation (Year 1/3)
Purpose

In the co-creative workshop, the consortium will come together for the joint creative **processing of research questions** relating to OXIPROs enzyme targets, product applications and value chains. Outcomes of this, including the specification sheets on enzyme, process, and product requirements for each of the innovation cases, will be used to develop surveys and questionnaires that will also enter and might influence work within WP2-WP4.

Further use:
 Round table talks

Key stakeholders
Influencers
Interested stakeholders
Passive stakeholders

OXIPRO

We are looking for stakeholders from research, industry, society and policy. Contacts can be from regional, national or international communities. If you can provide relevant mailing lists, please add the full name and contact information to the list holder.

Research: Colleagues, employees, cooperation partners, infrastructure, networks, etc.
Industry: Representatives of industry, associations, clusters etc.
Society: user of knowledge, technology or innovations, consumer associations, any potential user from you know who might be interested
Policy: Local, national, European, or any other international authorities, policy officer or policy maker, regulatory bodies, etc.

As names are sometimes ambiguous in terms of gender, please indicate the gender if possible

Level of POWER to influence OXIPRO positively or negatively?

Level of INTEREST in OXIPRO?

Can we refer to you when contacting this person?

Any hints we should consider/know about this stakeholder?

Name	Surname	Gender (if applicable)	E-Mail	Power	Interest	Can we refer to you when contacting this person?	Your Name	Comments / Hints
E	X	Female	test	unknown	medium	No	Name	no interest in newsletter would be grat to have on board
F	Y	Male	test1@	medium	unknown	No	name	
G	Z	X	test2@	low	high	Yes	name	handle with care
H	W	Female	test3@	high	low	Yes	name	important partner

OXIPRO sb science management

5.2 Mitigation actions to address the delays in D1.3

In a follow up meeting to the annual consortium meeting, NORCE (coordinator) and SBSM met to discuss solution to overcome the delay and misunderstandings in respect to expected internal support to the activities.

SBSM implemented additional webinars to inform about the planned activities, the partners' role and the importance of their contributions.

SBSM changed the strategy for communication within the consortium and adjusted and simplified e.g., data sheets and information.

In respect to missing input for data collection on stakeholder contacts, SBSM simplified the template for the stakeholder list (Excel sheet) to be filled in by the consortium members. SBSM and NORCE were calling for data sheets to be returned by the end of October so that categorisation can be undertaken. In addition, from September 2022, SBSM invited all beneficiaries to short information meetings (cappuccino talks) to explain the stakeholder data collection procedure and the request for data submission. These informal meetings were taking place with each consortium partner until early October 2022. The purpose of these cappuccino meetings is to involve partners more proactively in the process of stakeholder engagement. These flashlight meetings enabled the partners to catch up with stakeholder engagement activities or ask questions if needed. These meetings were taking place for each measure in form of short 15-minute presentations during lunch or coffee break time and were done with each partner individually.

Following the feedback resulting from an initial test mailing in the SBSM network in May 2022, a new, shorter letter was sent to the stakeholders collected from the partners in November 2022, asking for informal consent and participation in the surveys and other future activities.

Due to the lack of clarity in the preparation phase of the side event, SBSM (in agreement with the coordinator) changed the topic of the side event at the annual consortium meeting to clarify the planned measures around stakeholder engagement. In order to raise the awareness of the consortium members to better understand the stakeholder needs and wishes, SBSM organized a persona modeling session with the consortium for the different product groups of OXIPRO. In addition, the four innovation groups held a meeting with SBSM in early October 2022 to determine questions for product-specific surveys and questionnaires that SBSM and LEITAT were planning to send to stakeholders. This was done through an iterative process that began with collecting data, developing questions, formally agreeing these questions with the innovation group leaders, and finally sending the questions to specific stakeholders.

Feedback from these surveys were analysed and used for co-design as planned.

5.3 References

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